

THE STRUCTURE AND TYPES OF THE FOOT MECHANISM OF MODERN SEWING MACHINES

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The rail works with a presser foot, which must press the fabric to the rail with a certain force over its entire area. The foot unit has an adjustable spring for this, as well as parts that lift the foot and lower it onto the fabric. The presser foot can have a movable sole or a swinging one on a hinge. Such feet are convenient because they allow you to easily pass through thick places.

The foot unit has the following device (Fig. 1). The presser foot 8 is attached with a screw to the rod 7. A spiral spring 2 is put on above the spring holder 4, onto which the adjusting screw 1 presses from above. Under the action of the spring, the foot presses on the fabric, the pressing force can be changed with the adjusting screw. If the screw is turned to the right, the spring, compressing, creates greater pressure of the foot on the fabric, and vice versa. To lift the foot, a lever 5 equipped with a cam is attached to the head of the machine with a hinge screw. If you turn the lever and move its cam under the lateral branch of the clutch 3, the clutch will rise and raise the rod of the foot and the foot.

The presser foot holds the fabric in place. It can also serve as a guide to measure distances, allowing you to stitch straight. Outer and inner the edges of the straight and zigzag stitch feet can also be useful for measuring the width of a seam.

Fig. 1. Foot mechanism: a — foot unit, b — kinematic diagram of the foot unit: 1 — adjusting screw, 2 — spiral spring, 3 — clutch branch, 4 — spring holder, 5 — lever, 6–7 — rods, 8 — presser foot

The feed dog feeds the fabric backwards. While the feed dog feeds the bottom layer of fabric backwards, the presser foot feeds the top layer forwards relative to the bottom layer. This is one of the reasons why the bottom layer of fabric shifts relative to the top layer and appears somewhat shorter. The amount of this shift increases if the pressure of the presser foot is too strong.

However, this feature of the feed mechanism can be useful if you need to fit a longer piece of fabric relative to a shorter one, stitch a piece cut at an angle to the grain to a piece cut along the grain or cross grain, or a piece of loosely woven fabric to a piece of tightly woven fabric. The foot pressure regulator is used to set the desired foot pressure. The correct pressure setting should be sufficient to hold the material securely, provide uniform feed, and produce an even stitch. Insufficient pressure makes it difficult to produce a straight stitch. If the foot presses too hard on the fabric, the teeth leave marks on the fabric and a noticeable shift occurs between the lower layer of fabric and the upper layer. This causes small gathers to form along the seam line. Many new sewing machines have automatic foot pressure adjustment.

In sewing machines, the foot must press the material to the surface of the table so that when pulling the upper thread, the material does not become loose. There are a wide variety of feet, and they change depending on the shape of the elements being sewn. Special feet exist for sewing on buttons, ribbons, zippers, for different types of hemming, sewing in piping, darning, embroidery, and so on.

Below we will consider some types and functions of sewing machine feet. Apparatus for creating folds.

The pleating machine looks complicated but is very easy to use. This machine allows you to quickly and easily create pleats on fabric. The size of the pleats and the distance can vary.

Upper feed with replaceable sole and two guides. This walking upper feed provides a soft and smooth movement. Thanks to the upper feed, the layers of fabric do not shift and wrinkles do not form on the fabric. The fabric is caught and moved simultaneously by the lower and upper feed. The upper feed is indispensable when working with materials such as knitwear, vinyl or leather. This foot is designed for sewing machines with a maximum zigzag width of 9 mm.

AcuFeed Quilting Foot for Split-Fold Stitching (Wide). The guide on the foot helps you topstitch edges, folds, and pleats. It is also ideal for split-fold stitching. The foot guide distributes seams, allowing you to sew exactly along the line. When combined with different needle positions, this foot is also suitable for adding decorative stitches along the seam and sewing on lace and trim.

Quilting feet of different shapes. There are several varieties - open, as well as closed feet for quilting of different shapes. Just in case, what is quilting - it is patchwork sewing, one of the varieties of applied art. In translation from English, quilting is quilting. Quilting includes various techniques - patchwork, as well as applique and embroidery. Of course, you can connect the patches with a regular foot and with a zigzag foot. But with a special klz quilting foot, the work will be easier, more interesting, and there are several different feet for different distances between seams and different types of rotation.

Applique foot. This foot is ideal for sewing appliques, which is especially used for decorating children's clothing and home decor. The recess on the bottom and the curved edge allow stitches to pass freely under the foot, both along straight and curved lines.

Concealed Zipper Foot. The Concealed Zipper Foot allows you to achieve professional quality when sewing in zippers. The foot moves the teeth slightly in front of the needle, which allows you to sew the zipper as close to the teeth as possible.

Binding foot. The binning foot is used to process edges with bias binding in one step. The snail on the foot wraps the strip of fabric and guides it in front of the needle. It can be used for sewing zigzag, decorative stitches or regular straight stitches. Bias binding from 10 to 14 mm is suitable.

Many modern sewing machines are controlled by computer programs, which allows you to make eyelet loops and embroider any designs and patterns. A large selection of feet, accessories and additional devices expand the capabilities of the machines infinitely, allowing you to perform any operation related to sewing clothes.

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